

Master thesis in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Automatic analysis of time varying metrical structures in music

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Abstract

Automatic rhythm analysis is an important area of research in Music Information Retrieval (MIR) as it aims to develop algorithmic models to study the phenomenon of beat induction, an action intuitive and almost instinctual to human listeners. Automatic methods to detect rhythmic as well as musical attributes of a musical piece like tempo, beats, meter are studied widely in the literature. In this thesis, we explore time varying metrical structures in music from the perspective of meter inference and tracking. Time varying metrical structures are a part of various music cultures and genres like classical music, African music, progressive rock music etc. This thesis aims to infer and track the musical meter of such musical pieces by proposing extensions to a data driven Bayesian model which simultaneously infers the tempo, beats and downbeats of a musical piece. It is shown here that by adapting this method for time varying metrical structures, the model learns probabilistic relations for transitions between different rhythm patterns and hence, metrical changes can be detected within a musical piece. Audio files (containing percussion patterns) and their annotations (containing information about the metrical structure) are synthesized to validate the approach. Novel evaluation strategies are proposed for this case, as the present evaluation measures do not incorporate the metrical inference accuracy for musical pieces with changing metrical structures.

Keywords: Automatic Rhythm Recognition; Bayesian Inference; Metrical Changes

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Rhythm, like harmony, melody and timbre is one of the fundamental building blocks that make music. Rhythms can be understood as the relations that are obtained in time between "identifiable sonic events having perceived durations" [4]. When listening to music, the listener *groups* the sonic events into motifs, themes, phrases, sections and the piece itself. At the same time, the listener induces a pattern of strong and weak beats which repeat cyclically and provide a pulse to the rhythm [5]. This recurring pattern can be viewed as the concept of *meter*.

Changing metrical structures are a part of musicians' and composers' vocabulary throughout different musical cultures, to add surprise and serendipity to their performance. Twentieth century composers as Igor Stravinsky and Bela Bartok have used extensive metrical manipulations in the music they composed. The term *metrical modulation* was coined in the 1950s, taking into account the music of composer Elliot Carter, which can be typically characterized as rhythmically complex [6]. The the genre of progressive rock emerged during the 1960s and can be described as having "experimental time signatures" [7], which can change according to the structure of a piece. There are frequent time signature changes in African music too which can be attributed to the fluent and versatile nature of African rhythm patterns [8].

1.1 Motivation

Automatic rhythm analysis is an important area of research in the field of Music Information Retrieval (MIR) as it aims to simulate the workarounds of foot tapping with music, an action very intuitive and almost instinctual to human listeners. The research in this area has originated from obtaining algorithmic models which aim to extract rhythmic information about a musical piece, consistent with a human listener's interpretation. This rhythmic information is temporal and is extracted in the form of tempo, beats, downbeats and meter, which convey musical as well as perceptual attributes of a musical piece. A good rhythm analysis system is fundamental to the MIR tasks of music transcription, key estimation, structural segmentation etc. and also has applications in automatic slicing systems of digital audio workstations.

Probabilistic Graphical Models are a popular framework to infer these temporal parameters, given an audio recording. Their suitability in this task stems from the fact that meaningful relationships between these temporal parameters can be captured through conditional dependence relations among the model's variables. Recently, a data driven Bayesian model called the bar pointer model [9] was successfully applied for the simultaneous inference of the tempo, beats and downbeats of a musical piece. It learns probabilistic representations of different rhythm patterns through an onset feature based observation model, which makes this approach scalable to the peculiarities of rhythm patterns of any musical style [2, 9, 10]. However, these methods need extensions to study the case of metrical inference and tracking in pieces with a varying metrical structure.

The ongoing research and advent of data driven, scalable approaches in meter inference provides a window of opportunity to study the case of time varying metrical structures in music. Changing metrical structures are a characteristic of genres such as progressive rock [7] and have not been studied widely in the literature to the best of our knowledge. We aim to study these changing metrical structures from the perspective of meter inference and tracking. We propose that these metrical changes

can be inferred and tracked by extending the bar pointer model to incorporate the notion of changing meter.

1.2 Objectives

The main goals of this thesis are:

- To adapt the bar pointer model to infer and track meter from music recordings with time varying metrical structures
- To look for a data corpus which contains instances with time varying metrical structures
- To propose evaluation strategies for comparing metrical inference output for this case

1.3 Structure of the Report

We have done a literature review of the state of the art in automatic rhythm analysis tasks and can be found in Section 2. It also includes a review of meter related concepts, datasets, evaluation measures and libraries used for the task of rhythm analysis. Section 3 encapsulates the methodology we adopted to particularly study the case of time varying metrical structures. It also explains the process of generating the percussive dataset and the description of the chosen method and proposed evaluation measures. Section 4 contains the experimental setup, results and their explanations. Section 5 contains the conclusions from this work and some future problems that can be a natural continuation to the work done in this thesis.

Chapter 2

Background

This chapter provides a technical overview of the research in the area of automatic rhythm analysis relevant to the work done in this thesis. As very limited research on time varying metrical structures exists from an automatic rhythm analysis point of view, this chapter mainly focuses on exploring scalable automatic approaches that can be applied to infer metrical attributes from such pieces. This chapter starts with a review of musical concepts and nomenclature relevant to the thesis whose meaning will remain constant throughout the thesis. Automatic algorithms aimed to extract rhythmic attributes from a musical piece are discussed. Conventional signal processing based approaches and the current state of the art in probabilistic graphical models and deep learning are explored. Datasets and evaluation strategies currently used to validate these approaches are discussed.

2.1 Definitions and review of concepts

Humans listeners have an innate cognitive ability to infer a particular rhythmic interpretation of a musical excerpt. *Beat induction* is the cognitive mechanism of a human listener tapping their foot in conjunction with the rhythm of a musical piece. This rhythmic information is essentially embodied in the *meter* of the piece as it not only decides the basic rhythm of the foot but also the rhythmic arrangement of pulses, phrases and melodies. Meter is a musical as well as cognitive construct in which recurring beats are perceived as being part of a particular *group* [5].

Meter can be organized into hierarchical levels of differing temporal periodicities - the *tatum*, the *tactus*, and the *measure* [11]. Tatum is the fastest repetition rate of musical events. One level higher, the *tactus* is typically the foot tapping rate and can also be used interchangeably with the word *beat*. The *measure* (or *bar*) is the repeating rhythmic entity on which beats can be counted cyclically and the numerical length of the bar indicates the *time signature* of the excerpt. Time signature also provides information about the relative duration between the beats. *Period* is the time duration between successive beats and *phase* is the position of the occurrence of a beat with respect to the beginning of the piece. *Tempo* is the speed of a musical piece with respect to the beat level. Figure 1 explains the above concepts.

Figure 1: Depicting the metrical hierarchy [1]

An *accent* is an emphasis or stress placed on a particular event to highlight a particular moment in music. Accents at beats where they would usually occur are said to be *syncopated*. A *downbeat* is the most emphasized beat of the bar and is generally the first one. *Upbeats* are all the beats except downbeats. A *metrical position* is the numerical position of a beat when beats are counted cyclically with the meter.

Meter can be classified on the basis of number of beats per bar such as the *duple* meter contains two beats in a bar and the *triple* meter contains three beats in a bar. Similarly, a *septuple* meter means that there are seven beats in one bar. However, this meter could be accentuated by different kinds of stress patterns, such as "triple + duple + duple", "duple + triple + triple" etc. Hence, higher meters

like the septuple meter can also be viewed as a mixture of these smaller components - duple and triple. It is here that the difference between concepts of time signature and meter can be understood, as meter is about these smaller components and how they are grouped together, while time signature used is a symbol to represent the length of the repeating cycle and the relative duration of beats.

Research in automatic rhythm analysis comprises of studying this task at the above levels of metrical hierarchy. *Tempo estimation* aims to estimate the time between predominant pulses at the beat level. *Beat tracking* is the task of identifying all the beat positions where a listener is likely to tap their foot [12]. *Downbeat tracking* refers to identifying the position of downbeats in each bar of a musical piece [13]. *Meter tracking* aims to estimate the possibly time varying tempo, the beat and downbeat locations, given prior information about expected rhythm in the musical piece [9]. Similarly, *meter inference* [9] aims to identify the rhythm pattern, time varying tempo, beat locations along with the metrical position of each beat.

2.2 Literature Review

The aim of automatic rhythm analysis is to extract information about the rhythmic properties of music like tempo, the position of beats and meter of the piece etc., given an audio recording. Research in automatic rhythm analysis has evolved from pure signal processing approaches to data driven approaches combined with signal processing methods. Though most of the literature deals with finding this temporal information for different styles of Western Music like the music of The Beatles [14], Ballroom dance music [2], research was applied recently to study rhythms in non-eurogenetic music traditions such as Indian Art music, Turkish Makam music, Cretan Music etc [9, 10].

2.2.1 Conventional approaches

Conventional algorithms for beat tracking [11, 12] use signal processing based approaches and have three main sub-components - rhythm feature extraction, tempo

induction, and beat tracking. The extracted rhythm features are typically based on different kinds of onset detection functions [15]. A good onset feature can be considered a good beat tracking feature because the perception of beats relies heavily on the played musical notes which can be captured easily by onset features. The most commonly used onset feature is *spectral flux*, which is a measure of how quickly the power spectrum is changing. The dominant tempo [16] is then found by identifying periodicities within the extracted features through autocorrelation [12] and Time Interval histogram [17] methods. The beat phase, beat and non-beat observations can be identified, usually using this detected tempo to successfully extract beat instants by dynamic programming [18] and probabilistic models [11]. A comprehensive overview of beat tracking algorithms is given by [17].

A classic example of a such a beat tracker is the BeatRoot system, proposed by [12]. It has two major components which perform tempo induction and beat tracking respectively. Inter Onset Intervals (IOIs) are calculated after detecting onset positions and tempo hypotheses are obtained. These hypotheses and IOIs are the input to a beat tracking subsystem, which uses a multiple hypotheses search to test different hypotheses about the rate and timing of beats, to output the sequence of beat times which are the best fit to the rhythmic onsets.

A multi resolution audio similarity matrix (ASM) based method that estimates the time signature of a musical piece is described in [19]. The method uses the repetitive structure of music as the same bar repeats several times in the musical piece. An onset feature is calculated and multiple ASMs are generated for longer (bar) as well as shorter (fraction of a beat) times and compared to arrive at the best ASM and hence the time signature of the piece. This method is improved in [18], in which the beats are first identified and multiple ASMs only corresponding to the beats of the piece are generated. Dynamic programming is used to arrive at a beat similarity matrix S which denotes the similarity among all beats, with each other. Possible meter candidates are found by processing the diagonals of the matrix S . The median of identified musical meter candidates is computed and compared with a dataset of 361 songs in which possible meters range from duple, triple and a few

pieces of complex meter (5,7,9 etc.). This works also describes the case of the song "Superconductor" by Rush, a popular progressive rock band, which is played in septuple meter and can be broken down as "triple + quadruple" meter. By the proposed beat similarity among different bars, the two component *sections* (triple and quadruple) are identified and also the additive meter (septuple) is identified.

An approach for meter analysis is proposed by [11], where accent signals aimed to emphasize onsets are calculated in four frequency bands. Periodicity analysis is performed on these signals through a bank of comb filter resonators. The periodicities thus found are processed by a probabilistic Hidden Markov Model (HMM) [20] which does a joint estimation on the three levels of metrical hierarchy - tactus, tatum and measure. Here, the task of estimating downbeat positions is considered part of beat tracking, resulting in joint estimation of beats and downbeats.

A limitation of these approaches is that the peculiarities of culture specific music like non constant rhythms, syncopations, swing etc are not captured and as a result, the performance suffers for musical pieces that incorporates these elements. Contrary to the approaches, data driven approaches can offer us a unique standalone solution to capture variabilities and peculiarities of different musical styles. An advantage of such an approach is that same approach can be applied across different musical styles to capture style specific characteristics without the need of feature or parameter tuning. Data driven approaches are discussed later in this section.

2.2.2 Probabilistic Graphical Models

Probabilistic graphical models are a popular framework to tackle the metrical inference problem [2, 3, 9, 21]. Since probabilistic models can relate sequential audio data (from extracted features) through conditional (in)dependence relations, they are well suited for the probabilistic modeling of rhythmic patterns and metrical structures to encode different components (tempo, beats, rhythm pattern) of rhythm in music. These models also offer a unified approach to rhythm analysis as these temporal rhythmic attributes (tempo, beats, downbeats and rhythm pattern) can be simul-

taneously inferred. This kind of system exploits the mutual dependencies among these variables, but at the same time it has the drawback of having a huge state space which increases computational cost of the system [2, 21].

An important work in the area of probabilistic modeling of rhythm patterns for MIDI and raw data is the dynamic bar pointer model, proposed in [21]. It serves as the backbone to a lot of state of the art algorithms for meter analysis [3, 10]. The idea behind modeling probabilistic relations is that for a given rhythmic pattern, there are some locations in a bar at which an onset is more probable than other locations. This location inside a bar is modeled through the dynamic bar-pointer model which hypothesizes that the bar pointer traverses a bar and the state of this bar pointer is described by the following hidden variables: the "velocity" and the position inside a bar. These variables are bound together by meaningful conditional dependence and independence relations and can be inferred by maximizing the posterior probability of the hidden states given the observation sequence. Two observation models, one for MIDI data and the other for raw data are proposed. It is shown for two musical pieces that the model is able to detect change in meter, while tracking the tempo.

The work done in [2] builds upon the above bar pointer model and proposes a Hidden Markov Model (HMM) [20] based system which simultaneously extracts tempo, beats and downbeats from an audio recording. An observation model is proposed for a spectral flux based feature which represents the audio information in two frequency bands and models these observation probabilities as a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) for equidistant positions in a bar for every rhythm pattern. The influence of explicitly learning rhythmic patterns on beat and downbeat tracking results is investigated on a dataset of Ballroom dance music which contains excerpts from different dance styles. It is shown that tempo doubling and halving errors (*octave errors*) are reduced drastically in beat tracking performance and also that downbeat tracking performance improves over other state of the art methods. Another merit of this data driven approach is that the model is scalable to any kind of rhythmic style as rhythm patterns can be learned directly from data. Figure 2 represents mean onset features for two of these dance styles - Jive and Tango. For example,

the jive dance pattern displays which strong accents in the second and fourth beats and the characteristic swing can be seen in the high frequency mean onset feature.

Figure 2: Mean onset feature of Jive and Tango newline dance patterns [2]

A method for metrical inference and tracking in culturally diverse datasets of Indian Art music, Turkish Makam music and Cretan Music is provided in [9]. All three styles make use of rhythmic patterns that deviate from popular Eurogenetic music. Their approach presents a method based on the HMM model, similar to the one in [2, 3, 21] and also allows for metrical inference even when the rhythm pattern is not known in advance. The concept of a rhythm class incorporating several rhythm patterns is introduced here. It is demonstrated that by adapting the model to specific styles, beats and downbeats can also be tracked in odd time signatures like $9/8$ or $7/8$, which can be present in these studied musical styles. For inference of the most likely path of hidden variables, an exact inference is carried out through Viterbi Decoding as in [2].

A Particle Filter [22] based approximate inference method for meter tracking is proposed in [23, 24]. The system used here is the one in [9]. For a dataset of South Indian Carnatic music, it is demonstrated for that the computational complexity is greatly reduced by using Particle Filters for inference in comparison to HMMs, while maintaining the same order of meter tracking accuracy. In exact inference methods, the tempo needs to be discretized on a very fine grid for accurate performance, which leads to a large state space and as a result, a larger computation time.

A multi model approach is presented in [3], which represents the intricacies of different musical styles by training an array of Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), each with different chunks of the training dataset corresponding to different styles/genres of music. The feature used here is a spectral flux based onset detection function.

Figure 3: The multi-modal beat tracking system [3]

From this array of RNNs, the most suited "beat-activation function" is identified and is fed to a Dynamic Bayesian Network (DBN) similar to [9], to jointly infer the most dominant tempo, beat and downbeat locations. Although these neural networks have higher computation cost in terms of training and inference times, they are applied throughout the field of MIR for various problems like instrument classification, melody extraction etc. Their advantages are that their performance is very high and they reduce the need of feature engineering.

2.2.3 Deep Learning

Recent interest has also been to explore deep neural networks for meter analysis. One of these approaches for downbeat tracking is presented in [13] which uses a pulse estimation approach to segment the signal into short temporal units that can be interpreted as tatums. In the proposed system, the signal is represented as a function of six musical attributes contributing to the grouping of beats into a bar, namely harmony, timbre, low-frequency content, rhythmic pattern, and local similarity in timbre and harmony. Higher level representations of these features are then learned by corresponding deep neural networks and the downbeat sequences are finally obtained through a temporal decoding step based on the Viterbi Algorithm. It is showed that the performance increases as more features are added. For the tem-

poral decoding step, a simple model constrained to only one possible time signature and a model that incorporates more complex time signatures are compared, where the second model performs better as expected. This work was extended by using feature adapted convolutional neural networks in [25] which improved the performance of the system.

2.3 Datasets

To validate these automatic algorithms, ground truth annotations are required in the form of time instants of beats in the musical excerpt. Additionally, the tempo, metrical position of the beat and downbeat positions also need to be annotated according to the problem - tempo tracking/ downbeat tracking/ meter tracking etc.

The audio excerpt in time domain and its spectrogram can be visualised using tools like Sonic Visualizer [26]. Beat locations can first be obtained by recording the tap locations of the musical excerpt and then manually correcting these locations for exact onsets. Annotators can also follow a semi-automatic process, for example in GTZAN Dataset [27], beats and downbeats were first obtained through the ircam-beat software [28] and then errors were manually corrected by human annotators.

A very commonly used dataset for training and evaluation of rhythm analysis algorithms is the Ballroom dataset which contains beat and metrical annotations of several pieces corresponding to different styles of ballroom dance music. The SMC MIREX Dataset which comprises of "difficult" and "interesting" excerpts for beat tracking was introduced in [29] to include musical pieces of more complex musical styles and to recover from the overfitting of beat tracking algorithms by earlier datasets. These datasets don't incorporate the notion of time varying metrical structures. The Beatles dataset contains the beat and metrical annotations of all the songs by The Beatles, out of which a few songs have time varying metrical structures, mostly from 3/4 to 4/4 time signature and back. The Indian music dataset [9] contains beat and metrical annotations for pieces from Indian art music. It contains pieces with odd time signatures like 7/8, 9/8 etc.

2.4 Evaluation Measures

The evaluation measures for beat tracking are based on comparing ground truth labels of beat instants with the beat instants returned by the beat tracker. This result can be used to calculate metrics like F-measure, Cemgil, Goto score, PScore, CMLc, CMLt, AMLc, AMLt and Information Gain, used for the evaluation of beat tracking algorithms and are described in [14].

The *F-Measure* works on the principle of labeling an output beat as correctly detected (1) or not (0) and is calculated by computing the recall (R), ratio of correctly detected beats (within a tolerance window, usually equal to 70ms) and the total number of annotated beats and Precision (P), ratio of correctly detected beats and all the reported beats. The F-Measure is depicted by Equation 2.1. The *Cemgil Score* is similar but calculates a continuous score (between 0 and 1) for the correctness of each detected beat compared to the annotation. The *P Score* measures the accuracy of beat tracking by taking the correlation of annotations and detected beats to mark correctly detected beats. The continuity based measures (CMLc, CMLt) then further identify the percentage of the beats that were continuously correctly identified and are also recalculated considering octave errors (AMLc, AMLt). The Information Gain computes a beat error histogram comparing the annotation with detection to calculate Kullback-Leibler divergence [30] w.r.t. a uniform histogram.

$$F - Measure = \frac{2RP}{(R + P)} \quad (2.1)$$

As each evaluation measure captures the correctness of the output beat differently from each other, it is also demonstrated in [14] that the choice of the evaluation method can have a significant impact on the relative performance of different beat tracking algorithms.

For downbeat tracking, evaluation is carried out by calculating F-Measure (Equation 2.1). If an annotated downbeat exists around an output beat within a given tolerance

window, the output beat is marked correct.

2.5 Open source libraries

An open source library, *madmom* [31] contains implementation of various state of the art algorithms in the field of beat and downbeat tracking and meter inference. It incorporates low-level feature extraction and high-level feature analysis based on machine learning methods. It contains the implementation of various state of the art meter analysis algorithms [2, 3] which were submitted in MIREX [32] in the recent years and is available on github as python implementations which output the beat locations from an input audio file. Another open source library which contains the implementation for the work done in [2, 9, 10] is baysebeat.

2.6 Summary of the review

To summarize the context of the literature review with respect to the work done in this thesis, the research in the area of automatic rhythm analysis has evolved from tracking the metrical hierarchy of periodicities from the tatum to the measure scale. There is very limited research to address time varying metrical structures in music. Evaluation measures to check the accuracy of identified meter and metrical positions are not covered in the literature to the best of our knowledge. A data corpus which can be used to study and infer metrical changes does not exist.

Changing metrical structures can be found in genres such as progressive rock, which is characterized by "experimental time signatures" [7], which can potentially change during the same musical piece. Theoretically, a probabilistic model like the dynamic bar pointer model [21] could model such time varying characteristics in music by building probabilistic relations between rhythm patterns corresponding to different time signatures. The possibility of applying such models for the task of meter inference will be explored by synthesizing a percussion based dataset and checking the meter inference performance by proposing a few evaluation methods which capture the notion of time varying metrical structures.

Chapter 3

Methodology

In this chapter, we discuss the methodology applied in our research. It encompassed three main directions: synthesizing a percussion based dataset containing changing rhythmic structures, extending the bar pointer model to incorporate metrical changes within one piece, proposing novel evaluation measures for this case.

3.1 Dataset

As the particular case of time varying metrical structures within a musical piece is being studied, a dataset which contains such instances is required. As discussed in Section 2.3, the datasets currently used for meter analysis tasks are the Ballroom Dataset used in [2], Indian music dataset used in [9, 10] etc. These datasets contain musical pieces with a constant meter which does not change within the piece. The Beatles dataset [14] does have a few pieces with changing metrical structures, but they are not enough to carry out a data driven study. It has also been discussed in [14] that annotations for the rhythm analysis tasks are time consuming and require a lot of human effort. As a result, beat and metrical annotations of musical pieces corresponding to a specific genre/style are not readily available. So, a dataset on which a data driven study of time varying metrical structures could be carried out does not exist in the literature.

3.1.1 Data Synthesis

The issue of scarcity of specific kind of musical data representative of a specific musical style can be solved to a limited extent by synthesizing musical data (and its annotations). The process of synthesizing data is hardly time consuming and saves human effort of manually checking for correct annotations. While synthesizing the data, it is very important that the musical style or the property that we want to study is preserved. A drawback to this approach is that it does not take into account a lot of characteristics and nuances of music like acoustic conditions (like reverberation, echo).

We propose that such data synthesis approaches can also be considered a data augmentation strategy [33]. Synthesizing style specific variable musical data can help us to study variable cases and the boundaries of different automatic algorithms. In other terms, the applicability of an automatic algorithm can be examined on synthesized data and the outcomes can be studied to better understand the problem from a computational perspective.

When humans listen to music as a stream, percussion components and their variations are dominantly responsible for inducing the feeling of rhythm. It is also fairly straightforward to synthesize a percussion based dataset which could capture varying rhythmic structures. A percussion based dataset is also desirable because it ensures that the onsets could be identified easily to infer the position of the beats. In such a case, we could focus our study on the inference of changing rhythm patterns and issues it introduces to the current approaches.

Due to the advantages offered by data synthesis strategies and their relevance in our problem, we have synthesized a percussion based dataset which is representative of changing time signatures within a single piece. It is assumed that the rhythmic information is contained in the percussion component of the musical piece and hence, the metrical information is present in the flow of percussive onsets and their strengths. As the motivation of studying time varying metrical structures emerges

from such examples in progressive rock genre, we have imitated a basic acoustic drum kit (to synthesize percussion patterns), which is the primarily used percussion instrument in this genre.

3.1.2 Process of synthesizing data

Our data synthesis strategy can be essentially viewed as a random probability sampling of major attributes that make a rhythm, while keeping in mind that the synthesized data should represent the property that we want to study i.e. rhythmic structures. Although we have not tried to include commonly occurring phenomenon like syncopation and swing, the synthesized percussion patterns, upon listening, are able to convey the notion of metrical periodicities.

Human errors and timbre variability, which are commonly encountered while playing percussion instruments, were modeled to a limited extent - by allowing for *random* deviations in inter-beat intervals, in the intensity of the percussion component being played and also incorporating for a *random* slight misalignment of different components (kick, snare and hi-hat) at a particular beat position [34]. The amplitude of the first beat of every bar was kept the highest within the bar to incorporate the notion of downbeats and upbeats.

To create the dataset, several .wav files containing sounds of kick drum, snare drum and the hi-hat were downloaded from freesound [35]. For each synthesized audio file, the kick, snare and hi hat were randomly chosen out of the above .wav files. The groove of each component(kick, snare, hi-hat) was also chosen out of random out of a number of commonly occurring grooves in a particular time signature. The audio was created by placing these percussion components at their respective positions in an array and writing this array to a .wav file using Essentia [36]. A sample rate of 44.1 kHz was chosen.

Two examples of the audio files and their annotations can be found at <https://goo.gl/kiWvoj>. The python implementation to synthesize this data can be found at <https://github.com/kushshr/drumpy> as drumpy.

We created two datasets for this thesis:

- **SynthSet1:** First, a dataset containing 1000 percussive pieces was created. Each piece had two time signatures - 4/4 and 5/4, with the following parameters. The number and order of bars corresponding to different time signatures was *randomly* chosen. The tempo range was chosen randomly from 120 BPM to 230 BPM. This dataset will be called SynthSet1.
- **Synthset2:** Then a dataset of 1000 percussive pieces each containing three time signatures - 4/4, 5/4 and 7/4 was synthesized. The number of a particular time signature was *randomly* chosen for each audio file. Tee file always begins with a 4/4 rhythm pattern and transitions to 5/4 rhythm pattern midway during the piece. The tempo range was also chosen randomly from 120 BPM to 230 BPM. Lets call this SynthSet2.

3.2 Selected Approach

Any data driven model that aims to capture rhythmic information should work on sequential data to learn and describe their temporal relationships. Probabilistic graphical models like Dynamic Bayesian Networks (DBN), as shown in [2, 9] can preserve this temporal information through conditional dependence relationships among variables that impart the characteristic of rhythm to a piece.

3.2.1 Bar Pointer Model

In this subsection, we elaborate on the bar-pointer model which is a DBN at the core and infers the metrical structure in an audio excerpt. The approach described here was successfully applied in [9] to infer and track rhythm patterns from Indian Art Music, Greek Music and Cretan Music.

In a DBN, it is assumed that a sequence of observed data $y_{1:k} = \{y_1, \dots, y_k\}$ is generated by a set of hidden variables $x_{1:k} = \{x_1, \dots, x_k\}$, where k is the number of frames in the audio file. In a DBN, the probability distribution among these

variables factorizes as:

$$P(y_{1:k}|x_{0:k}) = P(x_0) \cdot \prod_{k=1}^K P(x_k|x_{k-1})P(y_k|x_k) \quad (3.1)$$

Where $P(x_0)$ is the initial state distribution, $P(x_k|x_{k-1})$ is the transition model and the $P(y_k|x_k)$ is the observation model.

The bar pointer model describes the dynamics of a bar pointer which traverses over the length of a bar through a space of these hidden variables: tempo, rhythmic pattern and position inside the bar. The state of the bar pointer depends on these hidden variables.

Figure 4: Dynamic Bayesian Network corresponding to the bar pointer model

The components that describe this DBN are discussed below.

Hidden Variables

The bar pointer model describes the dynamics of a bar pointer which traverses over the length of a bar through a space of these hidden variables:

Rhythm Pattern: $r_k \in \{r_1, \dots, r_R\}$

Here R belongs to the number of rhythmic patterns that are present in the data. The time signature of each pattern is indicated by $\theta(r_k)$. Each rhythmic pattern

belongs to a *rhythm class* and a rhythm class can hold several rhythmic patterns of the same time signature.

Position inside a bar: $m_k \in \{1, \dots, M\}$

$m_k = 1$ denotes the beginning of the bar and $m_k = M$ denotes the end of the bar. The number of positions (M) is calculated by $M = 1600 \times \theta(r_k)$. For example, for a time signature of 7/8, $M = 1400$ equidistant positions. The number of positions (M)

Instantaneous tempo: $n_k \in [n_{min}(r_k), n_{max}(r_k)]$

This is the rate at which the bar position progresses. The number of elements here corresponds to the number of tempo states and $n_{min}(r_k)$ and $n_{max}(r_k)$ are set depending on each rhythmic pattern r_k .

We know that any discrete state DBN can be converted to an HMM by merging all the hidden variables into a "meta variable".

$$x_k = [m_k, n_k, r_k] \quad (3.2)$$

So, these hidden variables are inferred through the observed audio signal by using an HMM which is described by three entities: A transition model through which the transitions between hidden variables can be described, an observation model and the initial state distribution.

Transition Model

Due to conditional (in)dependence relations as shown in Figure 4, the transition probability $P(x_k|x_{k-1})$ can be factorized as:

$$P(x_k|x_{k-1}) = P(m_k|m_{k-1}, n_{k-1}, r_{k-1})P(n_k|n_{k-1}, r_{k-1})P(r_k|r_{k-1}) \quad (3.3)$$

The individual components of the equation can be expanded as:

- $P(m_k|m_{k-1}, n_{k-1}, r_{k-1})$ The bar pointer moves from m_{k-1} to m_k and resets to

1 whenever it crosses the bar.

- $P(n_k|n_{k-1})$ is the tempo transition probability. If the tempo range is inside the allowed tempo range $n_k \in [n_{min}(r_k), n_{max}(r_k)]$, the bar pointer can accelerate, decelerate or remain at the same pace according the following distribution:

$$P(n_k|n_{k-1}) = \begin{cases} 1 - p_n & \text{for } n_k = n_{k-1} \\ p_n/2 & \text{for } n_k = n_{k-1} + 1 \\ p_n/2 & \text{for } n_k = n_{k-1} - 1 \end{cases}$$

Transitions to tempi outside the tempo range have zero probability. Here, p_n is the probability of tempo change per audio frame and was set to be 0.02.

- $P(r_k|r_{k-1})$ specifies transitions from one rhythm class to another. It is here that we contribute to the bar pointer model by allowing transitions from one rhythm pattern to other, but only at bar boundaries.

For example, given that there are only, two types of rhythmic patterns (A and B) in the data, the transition probability among them can be written as:

$$P(r_k|r_{k-1}) = \begin{pmatrix} P(A|A) & P(A|B) \\ P(B|A) & P(B|B) \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

Here, $P(A|A)$ represents the probability that the rhythm pattern will not change and remain the same. $P(A|B)$ represents the probability that the rhythm pattern changes from B to A. These definitions are similar for $P(B|A)$ and $P(B|B)$.

These quantities can be learned directly from data by counting the number of bars of a particular rhythm pattern and the number of transitions to and from that rhythm pattern. For the case of no change in metrical structure, $P(r_k|r_{k-1})$ is an identity matrix. For the case of changing metrical structure, the diagonal elements $P(A|B)$ and $P(B|A)$ would be non zero and would represent the probability of transition from one rhythm pattern to other.

Observation Model

The observation model aims to model the peculiarities of the metrical structure of a rhythm pattern assuming that there are some positions in a bar which have a higher probability of an onset occurring than other positions. The accents and syncopation events can also be preserved through the strength of onsets at the instants where they occur. The observation model used here is the one defined in [2] and is explained below.

Observation feature: A spectral flux based feature, LogFiltSpecFlux [2] is computed for two frequency bands. The STFT of the audio signal is taken for window size = 46.4 ms, hop size of 20 ms, DFT size of 2048. The logarithmic spectral flux is calculated from this STFT across 82 bands. As the bass onsets present in lower frequencies is important for modeling the rhythm pattern, the onsets are computed in low (<250 Hz) and high(>250 Hz) frequencies. The moving average is then computed and the resultant is normalized.

Figure 5: Illustration of learned rhythm patterns for 4/4 and 7/4. Mean of onset features corresponding to two frequency ranges is shown.

It is assumed that observation probabilities $P(y|m, r, n)$ change only at the 64th note boundary within a bar and is modeled as a set of $64 \times \theta(r_k)$ Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) for each rhythmic pattern. The component weight of each GMM are learned from data through Maximum Likelihood estimation. As these GMMs

are computed for every 64th note of for every patterns, it can be viewed as a direct representation of rhythm patterns. Figure 3.2.1 illustrates the learned mean of onset features for 4/4 and 7/4 based rhythm patterns. It should be noted that 112 ($64 \times \theta(r_k)$) GMMs are learned for a 7/4 pattern and 64 GMMs are learned for a 4/4 pattern.

Initial State Distribution

The Initial State distribution $P(x_0)$ can be used to introduce a priori knowledge about the system. For example, the knowledge about the preference of a rhythmic pattern or the tempo in particular culture can be imparted to the system a priori. For this dissertation, the bar positions and rhythmic patterns corresponding to different time signatures are distributed uniformly and the tempo is within its maximum and minimum limits.

Meter Inference

As discussed earlier, we are looking for the sequence of hidden variables that maximizes the posterior probability of the hidden variables given the observations, a maximum a posteriori (MAP) sequence $x_{*1:K}$ that maximizes the $P(x|y)$. The identified sequence of hidden variables can be understood as a sequence of the instantaneous tempi, beats, downbeats and rhythm patterns. Particle Filter methods are applied for this task in this dissertation due to their computational advantages over exact inference methods such as HMM inference [23, 24].

3.3 Evaluation Measures

A variety of metrics exist for evaluation of the beat tracking performance. These metrics are F-Measure, P Score, Cemgil, CMLc, CMLt, AMLc, AMLt and Information gain (D_g) and are discussed in [14]. The downbeat accuracy will be reported through the Downbeat F-measure.

We extend the idea of meter inference as the inference of tempo, beats, downbeats, rhythm pattern to also include the detection of metrical changes, if there were any. Apart from the evaluation of the detected beats and downbeats for which evaluation strategies already exist, the meter and metrical structures that are inferred from the above described system in Section 3.2 need to be evaluated. The identified position of the detected metrical change also needs to be evaluated. As the above evaluation measures do not incorporate identified meter and metrical positions, they do not offer a suitable representation of the meter inference accuracy. As this problem is not addressed in the literature to the best of our knowledge, we propose the following evaluation measures which can be differentiated with each other by the kind of information they provide about the metrical inference accuracy.

Correct Meter Percentage (CMP)

This motivation behind this metric is to compute the portion of the musical piece for which the meter was correctly identified. The sole purpose of metrical positions in this metric is to generate time slices corresponding to a particular meter in both annotations and detected output. The overlap between the annotated and detected time slices meter is taken for all meters. A quantity called *nEffectiveBars* is then calculated by using the tempo of the piece and meter of the overlapping time slice. The value of *nEffectiveBars* is summed for all meters to find the value of CMP. The idea of *nEffectiveBars* essentially represents the number of bars of the particular meter that would be present in the overlap.

$$nEffectiveBars = \frac{Overlap}{Tempo * Meter} \quad (3.5)$$

$$CorrectMeterPercentage(CMP) = \sum_{n=1}^{AllMeters} nEffectiveBars \quad (3.6)$$

Its range is from 0 to 1, 0 when the meter is incorrectly identified for the whole piece and 1 when the meter is correctly identified for the whole piece. A drawback

of this metric is that it shows a high value for musical pieces with a constant meter, if the meter is detected correctly. For example, if a musical piece contains one bar of quadruple (4) and 99 bars of quintuple (5) meter, and the meter detected is a constant quintuple for the whole piece, the CMP value would be very high even though the algorithm could not detect the metrical change. In such a case, this measure provides almost no information about the detected metrical change.

This metric is useful when the musical piece contains an equal distribution of the meters present in the musical piece (or dataset). Using this metric works for our synthesized dataset as we know that the dataset is essentially a random sampling with equal probabilities assigned to each rhythm pattern, which results in a "balanced" distribution of meter. To calculate this metric for a dataset, the average value is computed across all files of the dataset.

Normalized Correct Bars (CCB)

As the metrical hierarchy of the measure is being tackled, an evaluation measure that labels a bar as being correctly detected or not has to be defined. This metric takes both beat and metrical positions into account to define an identified bar as a *correctly identified bar*. A bar is said to be correctly detected if the beats belonging to the bar are correctly detected and the metrical positions corresponding to the detected and annotated beats are the same. Borrowing this notion from the F-Measure, a beat is said to be correctly detected beat if it lies within a given tolerance window (70 ms) around the corresponding annotation. The total number of correctly identified bars can be calculated for a musical excerpt.

$$\text{Normalized Correct Bars} = \frac{\text{Number of correctly identified bars}}{\text{Total number of bars in the piece}}$$

We also define the idea of *correctness of continuous bars*, which is very relevant to this metric. NCB is a continuous measure in the sense that the so called continuity will cease when a metrical change is not detected at the exact position of change.

Hence all eventual bars are marked as wrongly detected. This is also a drawback of this metric as it will have a small value even if the metrical change detection was delayed by one bar. A similar example is presented in Figure 3.3, it never recovers from the break in continuity at index 85, as all the eventually detected metrical positions are different compared to the annotations. For pieces with constant meter with correctly detected beats, this metric will have a value equal to 1.

Annotations			Output		
81	31.120	1	81	31.13	1
82	31.520	2	82	31.514	2
83	31.900	3	83	31.9	3
84	32.300	4	84	32.284	4
85	32.680	5	85	32.669	1
86	33.040	1	86	33.05	2
87	33.460	2	87	33.445	3
88	33.840	3	88	33.843	4
89	34.240	4	89	34.222	5
90	34.620	5	90	34.609	1
91	34.980	1	91	34.987	2
92	35.380	2	92	35.376	3

Figure 6: An illustration of an annotated and detected files

To calculate this measure for a dataset, its average value is calculated for the dataset. The pseudo code for this metric can be found at the end of this chapter.

Confusion Matrix

As portions of the musical piece are labeled as belonging to a particular rhythm pattern, the inference of changing rhythm patterns is similar to a classification problem in Machine Learning. A confusion matrix style evaluation measure is also proposed

along with the other measures.

The concept of *nEffectiveBars* is taken from the Correct Meter Percentage (CMP) metric defined earlier in this section. The overlap between time slices is calculated across different meters and *nEffectiveBars* are calculated for each overlap. These *nEffectiveBars* are reported as the elements of the Confusion Matrix in Equation 3.7. For the case of two meters, *A* and *B*

$$ConfusionMatrix = \begin{pmatrix} AA & AB \\ BA & BB \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.7)$$

where *AA* = Number of effective bars of meter *A* that were correctly classified, *AB* = Number of effective bars of *A* that were wrongly classified of being of meter *B*, *BA* = Number of effective bars of meter *B* that were wrongly classified of being of meter *A* and *BB* = Number of effective bars of meter *B* that were correctly classified.

A similar framework as above can be used to find the confusion matrix for more meters.

Normalized Inference Delay (NID)

It was observed during the experiments described in the next section, that these automatic inference algorithms show a finite delay in detecting a change of meter in terms of the number of beat positions it took the algorithm to identify this change. So, different such meter inference and tracking algorithms can be compared with each other based on the "time" taken by such a system to detect a metrical change. This characteristic of such a system also models the fact that human listeners also exhibit a delay in detecting such changes.

When a correct metrical change is detected, Normalized Inference Delay (NID), can be found as the difference between time instants of metrical change in annotations and output. A drawback of this approach is that it time-based and is hence dependent on the time signature and tempo of the piece. This metric has been

implemented for the case of two meters and will be discussed in the next chapter.

Algorithm 1 Normalized Correct Bars (NCB)

```

1: procedure NCB
2:   Choose initial  $z$  and  $\xi$ .
3:   for  $metr$  numMeter do
4:     for  $downbeatIdx$  AllDownbeats do
5:        $barsuccess \leftarrow 1$ 
6:       for  $metLevel$  metr do
7:          $downbeatPos \leftarrow OutputBeats[downbeatIdx]$ 
8:          $X \leftarrow downbeatPos - InputBeats[:]$ 
9:         Sort  $X$ 
10:         $minierr \leftarrow 1$ 
11:        Take absolute of  $min_{err}$ 
12:         $metDiff \leftarrow metLevel + 1 - downbeatMet[X[0]]$ 
13:        if  $metDiff * min_{err} \neq 0$  then
14:           $barsuccess \leftarrow 0$ 
15:        if  $barsuccess = 1$  then
16:           $correctBars \leftarrow correctBars + 1$ 
17:    $correctBars \leftarrow correctBars / TotalBars$ 

```

Chapter 4

Experiments and Results

This chapter presents the experimental setup and results for meter inference performed with the extended bar pointer model discussed in the last chapter. We report and analyze the results obtained and describe corner cases whenever possible.

4.1 Experimental Setup

The main goal of the experiments is to examine if the selected approach works to detect metrical changes. The performance evaluation is done by using evaluation measures reported in Section 3.3 to compare the inferred beats, downbeats and metrical positions. The values of the parameters used in the bar pointer model are as described in [9].

4.1.1 Experiment 1

Meter inference is performed on the SynthSet1 described in Section 3.1. Synthset1 is divided in two equal parts as a training set and a test set. Each bar corresponding to a particular rhythm pattern is pooled out from the training set and the bar pointer model (Section 3.2) is trained to learn probabilistic representations of each rhythm pattern in the dataset. Particle Filter based approximate inference as discussed in Section 3.2, is carried out on the test set to simultaneously infer tempo, beats,

downbeats and metrical positions.

4.1.2 Experiment 2

This experiment is similar to Experiment 1, except that SynthSet2 is used which has up to three meters per piece. The dataset is first divided equally - training and test set. Meter inference is then performed similar to Experiment 1.

4.2 Results

The performance of the beat, downbeats and metrical positions inferred through Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 is checked by evaluation measures discussed in Section 3.3. The evaluation measures are calculated for each file one by one and the results are averaged for the whole test dataset and are reported in the next section.

4.2.1 Beat Tracking Evaluation

Evaluation measures for the detected beats are reported in Table 3.

As both of the synthesized datasets are purely percussive in nature, the spectral flux feature can capture onsets very easily to detect beats. This can be demonstrated from the results as the values of all evaluation measures are very close to 1 for both the datasets, showing successful beat tracking which means that the detected beat locations are correctly identified throughout the dataset. This is desirable for our work as the main focus of this thesis is to study music from the perspective of changing rhythmic structures.

4.2.2 Downbeat Tracking Evaluation

The downbeat F Measure is reported here for both the datasets. As rhythm patterns change within one piece, the metrical levels can break in continuity (discussed in Section 3.3), even if there was a delay of one beat in detecting the metrical change. As a result, the downbeat tracking performance suffers. But, a finite non zero value

Evaluation Measure	SynthSet1	SynthSet2
F-Measure	0.99	0.99
Cemgil	0.95	0.94
P Score	0.98	0.98
Goto Score	1.0	1.0
CMLc	0.98	0.97
CMLt	0.98	0.97
AMLc	0.98	0.97
AMLt	0.99	0.98
Inf Gain	2.95	2.93

Table 1: Beat tracking evaluation results for SynthSet1 and SynthSet2.

Evaluation Measure	SynthSet1	SynthSet2
Downbeat F-Measure	0.32	0.2

Table 2: Downbeat tracking evaluation results for SynthSet1 and SynthSet2.

also indicates that the downbeat positions are correctly identified for at least the beginning of the piece and go wrong once the metrical change occurs.

4.2.3 Meter Inference Results

Performance accuracies on the meter inference evaluation measures proposed in Section 3.3 are reported here.

As described in Section 3.1, for every synthesized audio file, the number of bars corresponding to a particular meter are randomly chosen from a given list of possible number of bars. As the rhythm patterns have equal probability of occurrence, the dataset contains almost equal number of bars corresponding to each rhythm pattern. For example, in SynthSet1 (which contains two meters), each meter occupies almost 50 percent of the number of bars the dataset. In SynthSet1, the number of bars of quadruple meter are 9830 while that of quintuple meter are 10004, which proves that each meter occupies around 50 percent of the number of bars. This can be viewed as the baseline performance for any algorithm for our synthesized dataset.

Evaluation Measure	SynthSet1	SynthSet2
CMP	0.77	0.41
NCB	0.26	0.23

Table 3: Evaluation results for downbeat tracking for SynthSet1 and SynthSet2.

The **Correct Meter Percentage** (CMP) is first reported for both the experiments. A value considerably greater is observed than 0.5 for SynthSet1, which contains percussion patterns with two meters, means that the proposed approach detects correct meter for major portions of the musical piece. For SynthSet2, $\text{CMP} = 0.41$, which is also greater than the set baseline performance. Hence, it demonstrates that our probabilistic approach is able to capture the presence of more than one rhythm patterns within one musical piece and can also detect metrical change.

Each piece in SynthSet1 starts with a quadruple meter and transitions into a quintuple meter as described in Section 3.1. For SynthSet1, the value of **Normalized Correct Bars**, $\text{NCB} = 0.26$ shows that system is able to distinguish between different rhythm patterns at the beginning of the piece. In other words, the quadruple meter at the beginning of each piece is correctly detected for a few bars and then suffers a break in continuity around the position where the metrical change happens. A similar value of $\text{NCB} = 0.23$ is reported for SynthSet2. These low values proves that this measure is indeed a strict measure and its value depends on the continuity of said metrical positions. These observations about NCB also reinforce the findings of CMP, that rhythm patterns and their transitions are being learned through the selected approach.

The **confusion matrix** is reported for both the experiments in Equation 4.1 and Equation 4.2 respectively. Analyzing the confusion matrix for SynthSet1, we observe that number of effective bars originally in quintuple meter but detected as quadruple meter, is low compared to the other elements. This is because we only allow transitions only from a quadruple to quintuple meter for SynthSet2. It can be observed from Equation 4.2 that as we increase the number of meters in the dataset, the confusion among different meters increases and hence the performance

decreases.

$$\text{ConfusionMatrixSynthSet1} = \begin{pmatrix} 7225 & 217 \\ 1811 & 8945 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.1)$$

$$\text{ConfusionMatrixforSynthSet2} = \begin{pmatrix} 1328 & 1283 & 2130 \\ 1328 & 1642 & 1573 \\ 1205 & 1957 & 2955 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4.2)$$

Normalized Inference Delay (NID) measures the latency of an algorithm to detect metrical changes. This measure is implemented for the case of two meters and hence, works for SynthSet1. Its value for SynthSet1 is 0.19, which means that metrical change was detected only after a finite time had passed. Hence, it is shown that through the proposed approach, metrical changes are detected after a finite time with respect to the actual position of metrical change. Whether this issue of latency in detection of metrical change exists in all automatic algorithms or just our selected approach remains unexplored.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

This chapter concludes this thesis. The work done is summarized and the conclusions that can be drawn from this work are described. The main contributions of this thesis are also discussed. Unresolved issues that need further investigation are presented. The reproducibility of the work is discussed.

5.1 Summary of work

We started by introducing the problem of detection of metrical changes and set forward a clear motivation of studying the case of time varying metrical structures in music from a meter inference and tracking point of view. We provided an overview of musical concepts and definitions relevant to the thesis. We reviewed conventional signal processing and data driven approaches for the automatic analysis of rhythms. Particularly, we studied the evolution of probabilistic graphical models at length, as they are the current state-of-the-art in meter inference. The issue of unavailability of musical culture and style specific annotated data was also discussed.

We proposed and implemented extensions to a probabilistic approach for inferring metrical changes. Validation of the chosen approach was done by synthesizing datasets which contain .wav files with percussion patterns representative of such metrical structures. A review of the evaluation methods for automatic rhythm anal-

ysis revealed that beat and downbeat tracking evaluation measures do not convey information about the detected meter and metrical positions. So, novel evaluation measures were proposed and implemented to calculate the accuracy of the detected meter and metrical positions. We finally presented a detailed analysis of the results.

5.2 Conclusions

We have addressed the problem of meter inference in musical pieces with changing metrical structures, which has not received much attention from the MIR community in the past. Past approaches for meter inference assume a constant, "global" meter for each musical piece. So, we extended the definition of meter inference to also include the detection of rhythmic changes, along with the inference of tempo, beats and downbeats of the musical excerpt. We hypothesized that probabilistic graphical models like the bar pointer model could be used for inferring the position of metrical change in such pieces. It was shown that rhythmic changes can be detected by adapting the bar pointer model to incorporate probabilistic transitions between rhythm patterns.

To validate our approach, we synthesized a humanized, percussion based dataset which embodied the concept of changing metrical structures. This dataset can be essentially understood as a random probabilistic sampling of different percussion sounds and rhythm patterns. To humanize the synthetic dataset, we added random variability in rhythmic attributes like tempo, loudness of each percussion instrument.

We also discussed challenges in the evaluation of meter inference output. It was found that the currently used evaluation measures in rhythm analysis do not provide sufficient information about the metrical structure of a musical piece. So, we proposed evaluation measures to capture the idea of a non constant meter (and metrical positions) and showed that each of the proposed evaluation measures conveys a different aspect of the accuracy of meter inference output.

5.3 Open issues and future work

Although we have shown that the selected approach works to infer metrical changes, we have just managed to scratch the surface of the computational analysis of time varying rhythmic structures in music. Here, we discuss a few interesting and unresolved issues which we found interesting for further exploration.

- We proved that the bar pointer model can be successfully applied to detect changes in rhythm pattern. However, detection of the exact instant of metrical change remains unsolved. A probable reason can be the usage of approximate Particle Filter methods for meter inference. A possible solution is to use exact inference methods for inference as a larger state space could be beneficial for detecting rhythmic changes. Another continuation of the work done here can be to apply the Section Pointer Model which is capable of inferring and tracking different sections within a meter. Deep learning approaches can also be extended for detecting such changes.
- We consider data synthesis a data augmentation strategy and such synthesis strategies can be studied to expose other MIR algorithms to variable and style specific data. An immediate extension of the work could be to check the viability of such synthesized data, by comparing it with real annotated data. Listening experiments to validate such data for study could be conducted.
- Various aspects of meter analysis evaluation were uncovered and evaluation measures to incorporate metrical information were proposed. Objective evaluation strategies capable of capturing different aspects of metrical change need to be designed. Currently used evaluation metrics for beat and downbeat can accommodate metrical positions within their implementation. For example, the continuity based evaluation measures can be extended to have a condition on the equality of metrical positions, along with the conditions for correctness of beats as discussed earlier.
- Phenomenon like frequent tempo doubling and halving can also be found in

the genre of progressive rock. We believe that computational research on such a genre holds the key to study the rhythmic and melodic variations, which are commonplace in music of all kinds. Probabilistic graphical models like the bar pointer model offer a standalone solution to model such variabilities and transitions and can be studied to a greater extent.

5.4 Reproducibility

The links to the code written for this thesis are listed. The bar pointer model is extended on its MATLAB implementation in bayesbeat. Data synthesis and new evaluation strategies are implemented in Python.

Synthetic Dataset

<https://github.com/kushshr/drumpy>

bayesbeat

https://github.com/kushshr/bayesBeat_MetricalChanges

Evaluation Measures

https://github.com/kushshr/Metrical_eval

Additional evaluation scripts

<https://github.com/kushshr/AudioBeatTracking>

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